

Research article

First record of the flying fox bat fly *Cyclopodia horsfieldi* de Meijere, 1899 (Diptera: Hippoboscoidea: Nycteribiidae) on Ursula Island, Philippines

Ace Kevin S. Amarga^{1,2}, Michael W. Hastriter³

(1) Biodiversity Program, Taiwan International Graduate Program, Biodiversity Research Center, Academia Sinica, Taipei, Taiwan, ace_amarga061@yahoo.com

(2) School of Life Science, National Taiwan Normal University- Gongguan, Taipei, Taiwan

(3) Monte L. Bean Life Science Museum, Brigham Young University, 290 MLBM, P.O. Box 20200, Provo, Utah 84602-0200, U.S.A.

Abstract: *Cyclopodia horsfieldi* de Meijere, 1899 is an Old World nycteribiid bat fly primarily ectoparasitic to flying foxes (Pteropodidae). This is the first record of *C. horsfieldi* on Ursula Island, Philippines. This represents the first report of an ectoparasitic arthropod on bats in this protected area.

Keywords: ectoparasite, flying fox, Palawan, Pteropodidae

Introduction

Ursula Island Game Refuge and Bird Sanctuary is a small island in Southern Palawan that lies 20 km from the municipality of Bataraza (Fig. 1). The island is declared as one of the Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA) in the Philippines (Key Biodiversity Areas Partnership, 2022). As a protected sanctuary, Ursula Island is home to a variety of vertebrate species including *Ducula pickeringii* (Cassin, 1854) (grey imperial pigeon), *Hypotaenidia torquata* (Linnaeus, 1766) (barred rail), *Megapodius cumingii* Dillwyn, 1853 (Tabon scrubfowl or Philippine Megapode), and *Otus mantananensis* (Sharpe, 1892) (Mantanani scops owl) (Saulog, 1997; Matillano et al., 2008; Birdlife International, 2022). Also, Ursula Island serves as home to fruit bat species (Saulog, 1997) including the endemic *Acerodon leucotis* (Sanborn, 1950) (Palawan flying fox) and *Pteropus hypomelanus* Temmick, 1853 (island flying fox) (Tsang, 2020; Key Biodiversity Areas Partnership, 2022).

P. hypomelanus is one of the five species of flying foxes belonging to the genus *Pteropus* reported in the Philippines (Heaney et al., 2010). This species

occupies a wide geographic range spanning from archipelagos near the Indian subcontinent (Andaman, Nicobar, and Maldives islands) to Southeast Asia extending to Papua New Guinea and the Solomon Islands (Tsang, 2020). *Pteropus hypomelanus* is known to establish roosts on small islands and commonly on forested areas of nearby coastline (Heaney et al., 2010). Furthermore, *P. hypomelanus* is an important pollinator and seed disperser of tropical tree species such as *Ficus* spp. and *Durio zibethinus* Murray (Heaney et al., 2010; Aziz et al., 2017; Oo et al., 2017).

Prior to this paper, no published account of ectoparasitic arthropods have been reported from bats in the Ursula Island Game Refuge and Bird Sanctuary. This note presents the first documentation of a nycteribiid bat fly parasitic on the island flying fox (*P. hypomelanus*) from Ursula Island.

Material and methods

During a rapid biodiversity assessment conducted on Ursula Island in June 2019, an adult island flying fox (*P. hypomelanus*) was caught in the mist nets

Fig. 1. Location of Ursula Island in the southern region of Palawan, Philippines (A) and its beach forest vegetation (B).

Fig. 2. Island flying fox (*Pteropus hypomelanus*) collected on Ursula Island (A) and its associated nycteribiid bat fly, *Cyclopodia horsfieldi*, foraging on the chest area near mammary gland (B).

established at the edge of a beach forest (Fig. 1). Upon close examination, an adult female bat fly was observed foraging on its pelage (Fig. 2). The bat fly was collected using fine-tipped forceps and preserved in 95% ethanol prior to identification. The specimen was examined under Leica S9D dissecting microscope and identified following taxonomic descriptions provided by Theodor (1963).

Results and discussion

Cyclopodia horsfieldi de Meijere, 1899 (Figs 3–5)

Cyclopodia horsfieldi de Meijere, 1899. Tijds. Ent. 42: 153. Type locality: Java (Indonesia). Repository: Zoologisch Museum Amsterdam (The Netherlands).

Material examined: On *Pteropus hypomelanus*: 1 ♀, Ursula Island, Palawan, Philippines, 27.VI.2019, leg. R. Giganto & A. Santillan.

Distribution: Cambodia (Olival et al., 2013), Indonesia (Maa, 1962, Theodor, 1967), Malaysia (Theodor, 1967; Olival et al., 2013), Philippines (Theodor, 1963; Theodor, 1967; Cuy, 1980), Singapore (Maa, 1962), Thailand (Maa, 1962; Theodor, 1967;

Fig. 3. Ventral (A) and dorsal (B) profile of female *Cyclopodia horsfieldi* parasitising *Pteropus hypomelanus* from Ursula Island, Philippines (scale bar = 1mm).

Fig. 4. Lateral profile of female *Cyclopodia horsfieldi*.

Fig. 5. Some ventral features in *C. horsfieldi*: pronounced abdominal ctenidia (A); anal segment showing sclerotised region (genital plate) (B); tibia showing three middle bands and ventral setae (C).

Olival et al., 2013), Timor Leste (Maa, 1962), Vietnam (Olival et al., 2013).

Philippine host records: *Acerodon jubatus* (Eschscholtz, 1831), *Pteropus hypomelanus* Temminck, *P. vampyrus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *P. speciosus* Andersen, 1908, *Rousettus amplexicaudatus* (Geoffroy, 1810) (Theodor, 1963; Cuy, 1980).

The genus *Cyclopodia* is currently represented by 24 species and eight subspecies distributed across the Old World (Graciolli & Dick, 2018). In the Philippines, the genus *Cyclopodia* is represented by two species: *C. garrula* Maa, 1968 and *C. horsfieldi*, both of which are ectoparasitic on Pteropodidae (Cuy, 1980). The former is an endemic species parasitic on *Harpyionycteris*

whiteheadi Thomas (harpy fruit bat) (Maa, 1968) while the latter is primarily ectoparasitic on flying foxes (Theodor, 1959). *C. horsfieldi* has a wide distribution range spanning across mainland and maritime Southeast Asia and has been recorded in several countries.

Bat flies have been known to harbour various blood-associated microbiota and can transmit these microbes via blood feeding. Among these is the genus *Bartonella*, a group of intracellular parasites and the sole member of the family Bartonellaceae. Morse et al. (2012) reported genotypes of *Bartonella* from *C. horsfieldi* parasitic on *P. vampyrus* from Malaysia. The certainty of how many bat-associated *Bartonella* genotypes occur in Southeast Asia is still unknown and requires further research.

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